

The Breaking of Classical Mechanics Through the Lorentz Invariant $A = -Et+px$? Part 2

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In Part I, we considered that a given constant $v = dx/dt$ means that arbitrary and independent shifts to all x and t points are allowed because these do not change v , but change the trajectory. We pointed out, however, that the choice $dx \text{ shift} = \hbar/p$ and $dt \text{ shift} = \hbar/E$ does not Lorentz transform and so represents a different kind of physics than classical physics.

In this note, we revisit these ideas in a slightly different manner. We argue that classically there is no constraint on the constant shift to all x points and the arbitrarily different constant shift to all t points which leave v unchanged. Any constraint equation, we argue, which would lead to a relationship between these shifts would represent a different physics from classical physics because there is no a priori reason for any such constraint to exist. Thus, unlike previous notes in which we argued that \hbar/p , \hbar/E be considered an example of a shift set, here we argue that this a constrained set and so if there is a legitimate reason for the constraint to hold, some new, non-classical physics, should be present.

We consider the constraint $-E^2 + p^2 = -m^2 c^4$ ((1)) ($c=1$) and write it as $-Et' + px' = -m^2 c^4$ ((2)) using $x'/t' = v$. $v = x'/t'$ is a constraint which together with $(x'=0, t'=0)$ allows for any constant shift in x' and an arbitrary constant shift in t' while leaving v unchanged. Special relativity, however, maps m_0, t in a rest frame to (p, E) and (x', t') , so the idea of arbitrary shifts seems to contradict Lorentz transformations. The sense is that shifts in x' and t' should be correlated. This occurs for $dt' = \hbar/E$ and $dx' = \hbar/p$ (where \hbar is treated as some constant). This correlation, however, follows directly from ((1)) which is not based on any specific trajectory, but rather is a constraint on interaction variables E, p . Thus, we argue that a correlated shift in t' and x' is strictly linked to interactions and not the trajectory which allows for any uncorrelated shift in x' and t' . Instead of considering \hbar/p and \hbar/E as being an instance of a set of shifts (as we have done in previous notes), we argue that this shift, i.e. x', t' versus $x' + \hbar/p$ and $t' + \hbar/E$ is the same from the point of view of interactions (although not trajectories). This seems to imply directly that the time and position delivery points of an interaction (E, p) are not necessarily the same as the center of mass of the particle as described by its trajectory.

Classical Trajectory and Interaction Points

Classical mechanics is concerned with determining a trajectory $x(t)$. A trajectory, however, has to be measured and so we argue that E (energy) and momentum p of a particle are taken to sit at its center-of-mass. One may write for a constant velocity (nonrelativistic)

$$E = p^2/2m \quad ((3)) \quad \text{then} \quad E t - p x = 0 \quad ((4))$$

For a particle passing through $x=0, t=0$, the trajectory is $x=vt$, with x, t describing the center-of-mass. If $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + 2 \text{ constant}/p$, one would have a correlated shift in t, x which would leave ((4)) unchanged. There is, however, no reason for a correlated shift in x, t although any constant shift in x, t which is also applied to $x=0, t=0$ leaves v unchanged. The question then becomes: Is there any significance in finding shifts which leave ((4)) unchanged?

It seems that there is not, we argue. In other words, suggesting $\text{constant}/E$ and $2\text{constant}/p$ as special shifts implies no new physics even though these are correlated. In other words ((3)) is a definition of kinetic energy in terms of momentum p , but there does not seem to be any more general physical statement being made. It seems that there is no physical constraint forcing the constraint $\text{constant}/E$, $2\text{constant}/p$. As a result, we focus on special relativity.

Special Relativity

Special relativity may be developed for a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0, t=0$ and then at $x=0, t$. A Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{cases} |g & gv| \\ |gv & v| \end{cases} \quad \text{where } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((4))$$

transforms both $(0, m_0cc) \rightarrow (pc, E)$ and $(x, ct) \rightarrow (x', ct')$ ((5))

A Lorentz invariant for (p, E) is: $-EE + pp = -m_0m_0 \quad (c=1)$ ((6))

One may argue that ((6)) is simply a definition of E in terms of p and m_0 , like ((4)) (which excludes m_0). m_0 , however, is a rest mass, implying a rest frame in which $-m_0m_0$ is equivalent to $-EE + pp$ of any other frame. $E(m_0, v)$ and $p(m_0, v)$ and so v defines a frame. Given an $x=0, t$ in the rest frame, one has x', t' in the moving such that $x'/t'=v$ (for $x=0, t=0 \rightarrow x'=0, t'=0$). This means that the value of t governs the position of x' in the moving frame. In other words, there is correlation of x' and t' . Thus a shift in t in the rest frame should govern a shift of x' in the moving frame and one should not consider shifts to be independent in the special relativistic scheme. This contradicts the notion that any constant uncorrelated shift is allowed for x and t because this leaves v unchanged. Now ((6)) may be written as:

$$-Et' + px' = -m_0t \quad \text{where } t'=gt \quad ((7))$$

The trajectory is known to be $x'=vt'$ (with $x=0, t=0 \rightarrow x'=0, t'=0$). One may shift x', t' in any manner and retain v , but ((7)) suggests a correlated shift $t'+\hbar/E, x'+\hbar/p$ which yields the same result on the LHS side as x', t' . This shifted result does not represent the trajectory, nor does it represent a shifted trajectory. It is a shift which only applies to an E, p, m_0 relation which displays variables of interactions. In other words, we argue that this shift only applies to interactions, suggesting a separation of trajectory from interaction. We have suggested this in previous notes, but we argue here that this seems to follow directly from ((7)). In other words, the correlation or forced shift values \hbar/p and \hbar/E apply only to E, p interaction variables. This implies that a particle may move along as $x'=vt'$, but this does not mean that its interactions occur at the center-of-mass point, x', t' . In other words, the x', t' shifts from ((7)) are interaction based constraints and lead to a new kind of physics, namely one in which the particle moves along $x'=vt'$, but seemingly has a probability to interact at x', t' or in a range included in $x'+\hbar/p$ and $t'+\hbar/E$, as these shifts leave the Lorentz invariant ((7)) unchanged. We have already discussed in previous notes that the RHS is interpreted using $p \rightarrow 0, dx \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. In other words, there is consistency with this shift approach in all frames including the rest.

As a result, it is the sense of frame independence from special relativity which gives rise to the notion of considering special constrained x',t' shifts in the first place. This is why we have argued that there is no particular reason to take the constrained shifts of ((4)) seriously as there is no invariance there.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that classically $v=dx/dt$ implies that any constant arbitrary shift to x and t leaves v unchanged. In principle, one may choose any set of constant shifts, even correlated ones as we have suggested in a previous note, but there should be no constraint equation which implies a correlated shift, as this would imply a physics different from classical physics.

We argue, however, that this is exactly the case. The constraint equation: $-EE + pp = -momo$ ($c=1$) is based on $v=x'/t'$ (for $x=0,t=0 \rightarrow x'=0,t'=0$) and so may be written as: $-Et'+px' = -mot$. This is an invariant linking the rest frame (RHS) to all moving frames. Certainly x',t' is a solution. Any constant shift to x',t' would leave v unchanged, but change the trajectory. There is nothing new in this view. The issue, we suggest, is that $-Et'+px'$ suggests a very specific constrained shift: $x'+\hbar/p$ and $t'+\hbar/E$ which does not distinguish between x',t' in the invariance equation. This is not the same statement as a shifted trajectory. The invariance equation represents interaction variables, not trajectory ones, we argue. Thus, we suggest, that beginning with a relation of interaction variables, the x',t' shifts only apply to interaction and there is a degeneracy, i.e. x',t' , the trajectory point may deliver the interactions variables, or $x'+\hbar/p$ and $t'+\hbar/E$. In other words, interactions occur in an x',t' range which is greater than the x',t' center-of-mass point which represents a new kind of physics, i.e. free particle quantum mechanics. This follows directly from a constraint equation representing E,p,m,o . E and p are based on $v=x'/t'$ (if $x=0,t=0 \rightarrow x'=0,t'=0$), but the constraint equation implies x',t' shifts which are no longer arbitrary as they should be in classical physics.